

Table 3: Factor statistics

	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
Number of defining variables	9	8	3
Average Rel. Coef.	0.800	0.800	0.800
Composite Reliability	0.973	0.970	0.923
S.E. of Z-Scores	0.164	0.174	0.277
Eigenvalues	10.1882	1.8413	1.2576